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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR SIMULTANEOUS
DETERMINATION OF DECITABINE AND CEDAZURIDINE BY
RP-HPLC METHOD****R. Malavila¹, P.Aravindra Reddy²**

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Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024**Abstract:**

Introduction: An attempt has been made to develop a validated stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the estimation of decitabine and cedazuridine. Literature survey revealed that many analytical methods have been reported individually or in combination with other drugs. Retention times were decreased and that run time was decreased, so the method developed was simple and economical. It includes the general information on RP-HPLC and method development, general information on forced degradation studies and stress conditions like acid, base, peroxide, thermal, photolytic and neutral. Discussion: The article discusses about drug profiles and official status of selected drugs i.e., decitabine and cedazuridine. Results: In this article the previous literature available for drugs is used for developed research work which include stability indicating RP-HPLC method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of decitabine and cedazuridine in bulk and their pharmaceutical dosage form. Using Waters HPLC 2695 system, quaternary gradient pump equipped with auto sampler injector with 20 μ L is injected eluted with the mobile phase containing 65% 0.01 N KH₂ PO₄: 35% acetonitrile which is pumped at a flow rate of 1 mL/min and detected by PDA detector at 245 nm. The peak of decitabine and cedazuridine was eluted at retention times of 2.263 min and 3.001 min, respectively. Conclusion: In this paper, HPLC method for the selected drugs showed good linearity.

Keywords: Decitabine, Cedazuridine, RP-HPLC**Corresponding author:****P.Aravindra Reddy**Mother Teresa College of Pharmacy,
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INTRODUCTION:

A drug may be defined as a substance meant for diagnosis, cure mitigation, prevention or treatment of diseases in human beings or animals or for altering any structure or any function of the body. Drugs play a key role in the progress of human civilization by curing diseases. Today majority of the drug used are of synthetic origin. These are produced in the bulk and used for their therapeutic effects in pharmaceutical formulations. There are biologically active chemical substances generally formulated into convenient dosage forms such as tablets, capsules, ointments, and injectable, these formulations deliver the drug substance in stable, non-toxic, and acceptable form, ensuring its bioavailability and therapeutic activity.[1-10]

Decitabine:

Decitabine, a deoxycytidine analogue, is an anti-cancer medication classified as a hypomethylation agent. It is used to treat numerous neoplastic illnesses, including myelodysplastic syndromes, chronic myelomonocytic leukaemia, and acute myeloid leukaemia. Decitabine is a deoxycytidine analogue antineoplastic agent that belongs to the hypomethylation class. It is used to treat a variety of neoplastic illnesses, including myelodysplastic syndromes, chronic myelomonocytic leukaemia, and acute myeloid leukaemia.

Cedazuridine:

Cedazuridine is an oral nucleoside analogue generated from tetrahydrouridine that inhibits Cytidine deaminase and may be used to prevent the breakdown of cytidines. It is used in conjunction with cytidine analogue antineoplastics, such as Decitabine. Cedazuridine particularly inhibits the breakdown of cytidine analogues while increasing their bioavailability and potency.

Preparation of solutions:**Preparation of buffer solution:**

To make a 0.1% FA buffer solution, 1 ml of formic acid was mixed with 1 L of purified water in a 1000 ml volumetric flask, filtered, and sonicated. The pH of the resulting solution was 2.9.

Preparation of mobile phase and diluent:

A mobile phase consisting of 0.1%FA and acetonitrile in a 40:60 (v/v) ratio was prepared and sonicated before use. The same solvent combination was used as the diluent.

Preparation of standard solution:

Working standards of 35 mg Decitabine and 100 mg Cedazuridine were precisely weighed and transferred

to a 100 mL volumetric flask. This mixture was sonicated for 15 minutes before being diluted to the mark with 70 millilitres of diluent to yield a standard stock solution containing 0.35 mg/mL of Decitabine and 1.0 mg/mL of Cedazuridine, respectively. To create a working standard solution with 35 µg/mL of Decitabine and 100 µg/mL of Cedazuridine, add 5 mL of the aforementioned stock solution to a 50 mL flask and dilute to the desired level.

Preparation of sample solution:

Weighed ten tablets labelled as containing 35 mg and 100 mg of Decitabine and Cedazuridine, respectively, and computed the average weight. Transferred the tablets to a mortar and finely ground with a pestle. A powder comparable to the weight of one tablet was transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask. This mixture received 70 millilitres of diluent and was sonicated for 15 minutes. The additional volume was filled with diluent and filtered through a 0.45 µ syringe filter. To create a working sample solution with 35 µg/mL of Decitabine and 100 µg/mL of Cedazuridine, transfer 5 mL of the filtered stock solution to a 50 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the desired concentration..

Preparation of placebo solution:

135 mg of placebo was accurately weighed and put into a 100 mL volumetric flask, followed by 70 mL of diluent and sonication for roughly 15 minutes. The additional volume was filled with diluent and filtered through a 0.45 µ syringe filter. Transferred 5 mL of the above-mentioned filtered placebo solution to a 50 mL volumetric flask and diluted to the desired volume.

Preparation of calibration curve solutions:

An adequate volume of aliquots from the Decitabine and Cedazuridine stock solutions were transferred to seven different volumetric flasks. The solutions were diluted with a diluent to produce a calibration curve standard solution with concentrations of 3.5-52.5 µg/mL of Decitabine and 10.0-150.0 µg/mL of Cedazuridine.

Selection of detection wavelength:

Working standards for Decitabine and Cedazuridine were scanned in the 200-400 nm wavelength range using the HPLC's PDA detector. A better peak response was reported at 225 nm (isobestic point). In the current investigation, the detecting wavelength

Method development and optimization:

The primary goal in developing this new approach was to achieve an optimised chromatographic condition that resulted in acceptable retentions and

improved chromatographic peaks in terms of sharpness, symmetry, and resolution. Furthermore, sensitivity and selectivity were heavily emphasised in order to develop the optimal approach. Several systematic trials were conducted to investigate detection wavelength, column type, and mobile phase conditions such as composition and buffers. Before optimising column and mobile phase conditions, the detection wavelength was investigated, and 225 nm was chosen as the wavelength of PDA detection since both medicines showed good peak response at this wavelength.

To find an appropriate mobile phase, several ratios of water to acetonitrile and aqueous buffer to acetonitrile were tested. Peak broadening and tailing were observed during method development trials with water as the aqueous phase composition of the mobile phase. Instead of pure water, buffers such as OPA and FA were investigated in conjunction with acetonitrile as a mobile phase composition, however

the OPA buffer continued to exhibit poor resolution and inadequate retention. As a result, the only choice remained a mixture of FA buffer and acetonitrile, which was extensively tested in various ratios to determine the optimal approach.

Finally, the optimal chromatographic condition with better peak shape and resolution was achieved by utilising a mobile phase consisting of 0.1%FA buffer and acetonitrile (40:60 v/v) with an isocratic flow rate of 1.0 mL per minute. The mobile phase system was tested with various columns, including Symmetry C18 Agilent XDB -C18, and X-bridge Phenyl . The optimised mobile phase condition resulted in optimally separated peaks on the Agilent XDB -C18.

The optimised chromatographic peaks were achieved at retention durations (RT) of 3.152 minutes for Decitabine and 6.932 minutes for Cedazuridine

Table: Chromatographic conditions

S. No.	Parameter	Condition
I	Column	Agilent XDB -C18
II	Mobile phase	0.1% TFA and acetonitrile in 40:60 v/v
III	Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
IV	Wavelength of detection	225 nm
V	Volume of injection	10 µL
VI	Run time	10 min

System suitability:

The proposed method's system applicability was evaluated by injecting a functioning standard solution six times. The number of theoretical plates, resolution, tailing factors, and percentage RSD were determined, and the results are shown in Table 3.2. The results of the system suitability test revealed that the parameters examined were within acceptable

limits. The number of theoretical plates was greater than 2000 in all chromatographic runs, ensuring strong column efficacy throughout the technique development and validation procedure. Peaks were symmetric with a tailing factor of 2, and analytical results were reproducible (%RSD < 2). As a result, the system is suitable for carrying out the needed analysis.

Table : System suitability result of the proposed method (n= 6)

Peak	Statistic parameter	Retention time	Peak Area	Theoretic al plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
Decitabine	Mean	3.155	1166970	4663	1.05	-
	SD	0.003	8123.51	24.99	0.019	
	%RSD	0.101	0.70	0.536	1.790	
Cedazuridine	Mean	6.934	3251946	12145	1.08	12.34
	SD	0.003	15480.20	75.38	0.016	0.048
	%RSD	0.044	0.48	0.621	1.731	0.280

Specificity:

The chromatograms of blank, placebo, sample, and standard solution were recorded and examined for any interfering peaks at the retention times of the drug peak in blank and placebo. There were no

interfering peaks in the chromatograms of placebo and blank, showing that the formulation excipients did not interfere with the drug determination; this demonstrates that the procedure was specific. The

chromatograms for the blank, placebo, working standard, and sample solutions are shown in Figure.

Fig. : Specificity chromatogram of standard solution

Fig. : Specificity chromatogram of sample solution

Linearity:

Least square regression analysis was done utilising peak area versus concentration data to determine linearity. The method was determined to be linear for both analytes at concentration ranges of 8.75 µg/mL - 52.50 µg/mL for Decitabine and 25 µg/mL - 150

µg/mL for Cedazuridine. The r^2 value was found to be greater than 0.998, showing a strong correlation between peak area and concentration for the proposed approach. Linearity curves are shown in Figure and Table.

Table 3.3: Linearity data of proposed method

Decitabine		Cedazuridine	
Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak area	Concentration (µg/mL)	Peak area
8.75	312625	25	807382
17.5	606983	50	1634636
26.25	833648	75	2464573
35	1168352	100	3230368
43.75	1472647	125	4150921
52.5	1751941	150	4787679
Regression equation $y = 33072x + 11538$ $r^2 = 0.9990$		Regression equation $y = 32247x + 24314$ $r^2 = 0.9991$	

Accuracy:

Standard solutions with concentrations of 50%, 100%, and 150% of the working standard solution were spiked into pre-analyzed sample solutions and analysed in triplicate. The accuracy of the spiking sample solutions was determined by calculating their recovery at each concentration level. Decitabine and

Cedazuridine had percentage recovery ranges of 98.5-101.7% and 98.5-101.0%, respectively, with % RSDs of 0.39-1.53% for Decitabine and 0.46-1.11% for Cedazuridine. The approach proved accurate, with a recovery rate of 98-102% and a relative standard deviation of less than 2. The accuracy data is shown in the following tables.

Table : Accuracy of Decitabine

Recovery Level	Amount Spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount Recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	% Mean recovery \pm SD	% RSD
50%	17.50	17.73	101.2	101.2	0.39
	17.50	17.78	101.8		
	17.50	17.64	100.8		
100%	35.0	34.73	99.3	100.04	1.12
	35.0	35.48	101.2		
	35.0	34.87	99.5		
150%	52.5	51.72	98.4	100.3	1.53
	52.5	52.51	100.0		
	52.5	53.35	101.7		

Table : Accuracy of Cedazuridine

Recovery Level	Amount spiked ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount found ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	% Recovery	% Mean recovery \pm SD	% RSD
50%	50.0	50.52	101.1	100.3	0.68
	50.0	50.0	100.1		
	50.0	49.85	99.7		
100%	100.0	100.89	100.9	99.83	1.11
	100.0	98.53	98.4		
	100.0	100.05	100.2		
150%	150.0	148.52	99.00	99.50	0.47
	150.0	149.86	99.91		
	150.0	149.38	99.59		

Precision:

The precision method was evaluated in two ways: repeatability and intermediate precision, both of which were calculated using %RSD. Six independent assays of test sample solutions from the same homogenous sample were used to determine repeatability (method precision). The intermediate precision was assessed by doing six separate assays on the same homogeneous sample on two consecutive days. The %RSDs from the method precision study was 1.22 and 0.98 for Decitabine and

Cedazuridine, respectively. The percentage RSD values for the intermediate precision investigations were 1.13 and 0.98% for Decitabine and Cedazuridine, respectively. The results of both the repeatability and intermediate precision tests were within the acceptable range of not more than 2.0%, indicating that the created approach was precise and adequate for producing consistent outcomes.

The results of the method and intermediate precision are presented in Table.

Table: Repeatability result of the proposed method

Injection	Decitabine	Cedazuridine
% Assay		
1	100.2	99.1
2	98.2	98.5
3	101.0	99.5
4	99.7	101.1
5	101.4	100.6
6	99.2	101.1
Mean	100.0	99.8
SD	1.22	0.98
%RSD	1.22	0.98

Table : Intermediate precision result of the proposed method

Injection	Decitabine		Cedazuridine	
	Day-1	Day-2	Day-1	Day-2
% Assay				
1	98.7	98.2	100.3	99.3
2	101.8	101.2	98.5	98.2
3	99.1	98.4	99.9	99.5
4	100.5	100.6	100.5	99.3
5	100.0	99.4	100.7	101.2
6	100.8	100.1	101.0	100.4
Mean	99.8		99.7	
SD	1.13		0.98	
%RSD	1.13		0.98	

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation (LOD and LOQ):

LOD and LOQ determinations were done to test the method's sensitivity, which was measured using the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N). Analyte solutions with

lower concentrations were produced and analysed in triplicate. The LOD concentration provided a S/N ratio of 3, while the LOQ concentration yielded a S/N ratio of 10. The lower LOD values demonstrate the increased sensitivity of the approach.

Table : LOD and LOQ

	Decitabine	Cedazuridine
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.06	3.0
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	3.5	10.0

Robustness:

To assess the impact of the modifications on analytical result, minor variations in flow rate and mobile phase composition were deliberately introduced. To explore the effect of flow rate, the flow was varied by 0.1 units, i.e., 0.9 mL/min and 1.1 mL/min. To study the effect of solvent composition, the mobile phase was studied at $\pm 5\%$ from the nominal concentration of the organic phase, i.e., 55% and 65% v/v of acetonitrile. The results show that no

system suitability parameter strayed from the allowed level under all robust conditions tested.

Tailing factors were 2, plate counts exceeded 2000, and percentage RSDs of retention times were <2 . Slight modifications in the examined chromatographic settings had no significant effect on analytical outputs, indicating that the procedure was robust and dependable for routine analysis.

Table: Robustness data of the proposed method

Optimized condition	Robust condition	Retention time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution	%RSD
Decitabine						
Flow rate (1 mL/min)	0.9 mL/min	3.942	4727	1.07	-	0.52
	1.1 mL/min	2.644	4593	1.05	-	0.29
Mobile phase composition (ACN: Buffer, 60:40 v/v)	55:45, v/v	3.950	4706	1.08	-	0.48
	65:35, v/v	2.732	4615	1.08	-	1.13
Cedazuridine						
Flow rate (1 mL/min)	0.9 mL/min	8.835	12694	1.09	19.89	0.44
	1.1 mL/min	5.767	11996	1.11	15.42	1.06
Mobile phase composition (ACN: Buffer, 60:40 v/v)	55:45, v/v	8.726	12985	1.08	19.10	1.07
	65:35, v/v	5.036	12024	1.07	12.52	0.53

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The current analytical approach was established after investigating several parameters. The optimal wavelength for PDA detection was chosen as 225 nm because both medications showed a satisfactory peak response at this wavelength. Better separation with nice peak morphologies was achieved on the Agilent XDB -C18 column, hence it was chosen as the column for the suggested technique.

The optimal mobile phase composition for the intended investigation was 0.1%FA buffer and acetonitrile (40:60 v/v), which produced symmetric peaks with good resolution. The injection volume was 10 μ L, and the flow rate was set to 1 mL/min to achieve appropriate retention times. The run time was set to 10 minutes because peaks were observed at 3.152 and 6.932 minutes for Decitabine and Cedazuridine, respectively.

The developed approach was validated in accordance with ICH Q2R1 recommendations for use in the analysis of bulk medicines and formulations. The method's validation settings yield results that are within the prescribed limits. The system appropriateness results showed that the method was

reproducible and reliable for routine analysis, with all parameters such as %RSD, USP plate count, tailing factor, and resolution being within the acceptable range.

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